

Language and Terminology Issue

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Abstract:

Significant progress has been made in the field of language and terminology in the 20th century. This progress has led to advancements in various sectors including science, technology, engineering, and production. However, developments in other fields, techniques, technologies, and various branches of science and production have also contributed to this advancement. This article discusses the author's insights into the specifics of terminology and terminology, as well as their own views based on them. The author has drawn conclusions from numerous works related to linguistics, employing terminology, concepts, and other elements.

Keywords: word, term, terminology, lexical meaning, definition, lexicography, onomastics, onomasiology, terminology, meaning, content.

The study of terminology issues in the field of world linguistics began to emerge in the 18th-19th centuries, focusing on the content nature of the term concept. Scientists who support functional approach to the language discussed the relative nature of the term and sought to prove the conditional boundary between terminology and general vocabulary. It is known that a term, like other lexical units, serves a nominative function. A term is a word or phrase that demands a clear and stable expression of a specific concept in the field of science or technology. A term should be short, precise, and unambiguous, aimed at expressing a scientific concept (i.e., a specific field concept). Thus, the term primarily embodies adequacy (full compliance with scientific concepts about the object being described), clarity (the specificity of the term in the terminological system), unambiguity (avoidance of polysemy), and formal consistency (the reflection of the unique sound complex of the concept being expressed).

Terminology (from the Latin "terminus" - boundary, limit, and the Greek "logos" - word, teaching) is a branch of linguistics that deals with a collection of terms that express any field of knowledge or

activity or any natural language concepts, as well as the formation and operation rules of these term collections from a grammatical point of view.

The diverse interpretation of the concept of a term, the existence of more than three thousand definitions, and the lack of a precise definition are emphasized by scholars. Systematicity, monosemy, specificity to the field, are essential characteristics of the term, and the formation of the term is related to internal structuring, standardization, semantic standardization, and differentiation. A term differs not by being a special word form from other words, but by having a specific function. This characteristic makes it unique. In linguistics, the concepts of term, terminology, and terminological system, in every aspect, have complexity and specificity, and they are not uniquely shaped in their scientific definition and description.

The term (Latin terminus - boundary, limit) is a word or combination of words that expresses a specific concept related to a particular field of knowledge or activity. The term is passed down through a specific terminological system of the general language, and terms and words in general language complement each other.

The term (Latin terminus - boundary, limit) is a word or combination of words that expresses a specific concept related to a particular field of knowledge or activity. The term is passed down through a specific terminological system of the general language, and terms and words in general language complement each other. In Uzbek terminology, interest in studying terminology issues began in the middle of the last century. The research of S. Ibrohimov, S. Usmonov, S. Akobirov, A. Hojiyev, R. Doniyorov, U. Tursunov, A. Madvaliev, and others is noted as valuable work in the field of terminology. Researchers have deeply analyzed the linguistic characteristics of terms used in various fields in their research work and have raised the issue of organizing specialized terms. Interest in studying terminology issues in Uzbek terminology arose from the middle of the last century. The research of S. Ibrohimov, S. Usmonov, S. Akobirov, A. Hojiyev, R. Doniyorov, U. Tursunov, A. Madvaliev is noted as significant work in the field of terminology. Researchers such as R. Doniyorov, Kh. Jamolkhonov, A. I. Qosimov, D. Kh. Bozorova, A. Madvaliyev, Kh. Dadaboyev, I. Yoldoshev, Z. Mirahmedova, N. Mamatov, Ch. S. Abdullayeva, D. Adikhanov, O. S. Ahmedov, Z. A. Juraboyeva, A. Hasanov have deeply analyzed the linguistic characteristics of various terms used in different fields and have addressed the issue of organizing specialized terms.

In the field of linguistics, great attention has been paid to studying the terminological lexicon characteristics in the 20th century. The identification of terms and their linguistic status, as well as the advancement of terminology, have always been of great importance. The analysis of the degree of use of terms in language and speech, as well as their linguistic nature, etymology, formation methods, lexical-semantic characteristics, and their paradigmatic and syntagmatic relationships, has been one of the main issues in the field of world linguistics. The results of research conducted in the field of world linguistics have significantly advanced scientific knowledge related to terminological lexicon. Linguists have carried out numerous studies on the stylistic, lexical-semantic, and structural characteristics of terms, and this activity continues with great enthusiasm.

As a result of the advancement of science and technology, various terminological systems that are emerging have directed the new scientific paradigms of linguistics and have highlighted the need for scientific research in various fields. A term is a specific word, and it differs from ordinary words in that it is limited by various meanings, as well as being inclined to have a single, precise expression of concepts and objects.

In works related to terminology, in all scientific definitions of the term, its specific, particular concept is initially emphasized. In addition, in modern linguistics, lexical units that determine the development of terminological systems are explained in the language of intellectualization, as well as the increase in communicative importance of terminology, and the wide use of specific lexical

units that express concepts in language. This situation is considered a linguistic phenomenon that determines and constantly updates terminological systems in a dynamic manner.

In the Uzbek language, the processes of terminologization, determination, and transfer of terms, as emphasized above, are being observed, and Uzbek language terminological systems are developing and further advancing in all aspects as a result of the progress of science and technology. Since language is subject to the influence of society, culture, and time, the changes in place and time are the basis for defining terminology as an independent research object. It is known that in the process of the lexical development of the language, the general lexicon of the language is expanding, and its immutable part is being formed. Within this framework, specific types of lexicon are formed as specialized terms in the language of concepts that have emerged within a certain field.

Sometimes in linguistics, terms such as "istiloh", "atama", and "nomenclature" are used interchangeably. According to experts, the meaning of the term "atama" is broader than the meaning of the term "term". "Atama" is understood as the name of all things, while "term" is an official unit used in a specific field. It can be seen that the concept of a term is related to the concept of an atama that enters the lexical level. In A. Hojiyev's "Explanatory Dictionary of Linguistic Terms", the terms "term" and "atama" are given as synonyms. The term "terminus" (Latin: terminus – boundary, limit, mark) is used to refer to a word or phrase that expresses a specific concept related to a particular field of science or activity.

The term "terminology" refers to a word or phrase that precisely expresses a concept related to a specific field of science, technology, or other areas. These terms are defined within the scope of their use and are distinguished from general vocabulary by their precision and lack of expressiveness and emotionality.

Terminologiya (termin + logos – soʻz, taʼlimot) is defined in this dictionary as: 1. A collection of terms related to a particular science, profession, or other field. For example, grammatical terminology, art terminology, etc. 2. The branch of linguistics that studies terms. It is known that while the terms "termin", "atama", and "istiloh" are used interchangeably in some literary works, in some cases, the latter is mainly used in historical contexts.

As A. Madvaliyev noted, the term "termin" refers to words and phrases used in the fields of science, technology, or sectors, while "atama" refers to names given in a specific manner, such as nomenclature, especially geographic objects, place names (toponyms), and Arabic terms. Its use is related to the historical aspect of terminology and is based on the concepts found in historical sources.

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